

Seeding Fusion: The rising sun in the west.

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Abstract:

If the sun were to rise in the west contrary to natural law, it could create an illusion of the second sun, a path, for a moment for less than 10 seconds in a planned detonation of a pure deuterium-based fusion EMI weapon at high altitude for discovery an omnipresent fusion process, a potential candidate for a future energy source, and scalable armament.

In this article, we present an interpretation of many worlds that is based on superposition and non-collapsing wave functions and proves the simultaneous existence of two deuterium nuclei in superposition, which leads to a tunnel beyond strong, weak and electromagnetic forces, a theoretical demonstration of fusion at matter densities much less than the Lawsons criteria.

The need for sowing to achieve this coherence has been demonstrated analogously to the principles of cloud sowing.

Keywords:

HellBoy, Amazon Alexa, seeds, deuterium, heavy water, overlay principle, macroscopic tunneling, Lawsons Criteria, E8.

Könnte die Sonne im Westen im Widerspruch zum Naturgesetz aufgehen, könnte sie für einen Moment für weniger als 10 Sekunden in einer geplanten Detonation einer reinen Deuterium-basierten Fusions-EMI-Waffe in großer Höhe eine Illusion der zweiten Sonne, eines Pfades, erzeugen zur Entdeckung eines allgegenwärtigen Fusionsprozesses, eines möglichen Kandidaten für eine zukünftige Energiequelle und einer skalierbaren Bewaffnung.

In diesem Artikel präsentieren wir eine Interpretation vieler Welten, die auf Überlagerung und nicht kollabierenden Wellenfunktionen basiert und die gleichzeitige Existenz von zwei Deuteriumkernen in Überlagerung beweist, was zu einem Tunnel über starke, schwache und elektromagnetische Kräfte hinaus führt, eine theoretische Demonstration der Fusion bei Materiedichten viel weniger als die Lawsons-Kriterien.

Die Notwendigkeit der Aussaat, um diese Kohärenz zu erreichen, ist analog zu den Prinzipien der Wolkenaussaat erwiesen.

Schlüsselwörter:

HellBoy, Amazon Alexa, Samen, Deuterium, schweres Wasser, Überlagerungsprinzip, makroskopisches Tunneln, Lawsons Criteria, E8.

What:

Deuterium-Deuterium fusion by superposition is a viable candidate for applications like motors, weapons and thermal power. The field of computing with protons or protonics is introduced, with proton flow, either in diffusive media or in proton conducting polymers, as an experimental demonstration of deuterium fusion by superposition of macroscopic tunneling in two proton and neutron fusion reactions or a direct deuterium deuterium nucleus fusion reaction.

How:

Quantum superposition in many places theory is seeded in deuteronomic plasma, with a coherence for teleportation. Can this be experimentally demonstrated as a seeding process of cyclic teleportation of thousands of deuterons to the same position at strong and weak forces scales? Leading to fusion?

Why: The Energy Crisis, necessitates the innovation of new and renewable energies from sea water, given the abundance of heavy water, deutronics and protonics are viable computational sciences and with viable demonstrations of Quantum Teleportation in proton conducting gels, with the seeding of the coherence, and the positive probability of a bi-deuteron condensate, fusion may be demonstrable.

Code Base:

Amazon Alexa Story: (“Robot Check” n.d., “Robot Check” n.d.) Say “Alexa start sun stories”

Introduction.

Neutron stars have been described from heavy condensation of neutrons and other residues in the life cycle of a star, other forms of baryonic condensation have been described in astrophysical phenomenon, proton macroscopic tunneling has recently gained ground as a theory for fusion in the sun. Quantum teleportation opens up a new mechanism for condensation of deuterons, in this paper a mechanism of seeding the coherence for a deutronic teleportation based fusion reaction in deuteron conducting gels of single file channels is described as speculative theory, but with tangible calculations. Will experiments follow is an open problem, leading someday

to a pure nuclear weapon, a light as bright as the Sun in the western hemisphere.

Problem Definition.

Given the fusion reaction for the deuterium-deuterium fusion ("Nuclear Fusion" n.d.)

Superposition of wave functions of two deuterium ions in the superposition of flow transports against Maxwell electromagnetism and with strong and weak nuclear forces.

Given channel c there is an overlay of $\psi(D1)$ and $\psi(D2)$ for any two nuclei in the flow for transporting individual files in a flow of deuterium plasma.

If $\psi(D1, D2)$ is the superposition of these two waves, there is a likelihood of thermonuclear fusion in protonics or p^{++} , which corresponds to $(p + e)^{++}$, in the deuterium combination in $\psi(D1, D2)$.

Fusion is shown to be atomic in protonic transmutation by overlay, since fusion-based transprotonization or transmutation is coherent.

Background.

Fusion has traditionally approached with high energy physics defined by Lawson's criteria, while the field of cold fusion has been shadowed in a mask of pseudoscience, with no definitive repeatable experimentation. In the new era of teleportation based physics, would instability of matter teleportation in the same place as observable transitions from unstable clusters of strong and weak force agglomerations of nuclear soup to a stable rearrangement by fusion be demonstrable?

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Formal Definitions:

The atomicity in fusion is in proton fusion by superposition :

By E8 theory, we consider a Feynman path integral formulation for a single file conduction problem for deuterium or deuterium and proton plasma.

Given an adjacency of two deuterium nuclei $D1$ and $D2$, we assume $\psi(D1, D2)$ of the interference of $\psi(D1)$ and $\psi(D2)$ in adjacency.

[\(lvlev. B \)](#) describes a cusp driven tunneling phenomenon, in deuteron fusion at low energies.

We consider a path integral formulation for the superposition by quantum teleportation. Let $(r1, t1)$ and $(r2, t2)$ be the space time coordinates of $D1$ and $D2$ at the observed event of fusion at (r, t) , we prove that quantum teleportation by superposition through the many places at the same time observable theory applies to this kind of teleportation interpretation of tunneling through the coulomb barrier separating the deuterons in free media and polymer scaffolding in conduction.

The normal quantum teleportation, calls for the creation of $\psi_{D1'}(r, t)$ from $\psi_{D1}(r, t)$ as a new copy of the deuteron in exactly the same position as deuteron $D2$. Given this superposition by teleportation, it is highly likely that strong and weak nuclear forces will pervade at such quantum scales to create a redistribution of energy and an instability, leading to a stable helium nucleus with the release of energy.

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Discussion.

Future Work.

An experimental verification of the yield to 3.27 MeV from the reaction, in a deuterium lamp is proposed, with a D2 protonics seeding, a secret yet to be discovered. Several proton conduction gels are viable candidates for a superposition based proof of concept of pure fusion. Either free plasmas in a fuel cell like experimental setup or proton conduction gels can be used in an experimental setup.

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